

Role of Bowel Wash and Gut Sterilizing Agents in Recovery from Hepatic Encephalopathy

Neeraj Singh¹, A K Nandmer², V K Nandmer^{3*}, Simmi Dube⁴¹MD Medicine, Junior Resident, Department of General Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India²DM Gastroenterology, Assistant Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India³DM Neurology, Professor, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India⁴MD Medicine, Professor and Head, Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. V K Nandmer

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Hepatic encephalopathy (HE) is a severe neurological complication of liver dysfunction, frequently seen in patients with cirrhosis or acute liver failure. Bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents have emerged as potential treatments to alleviate HE symptoms by targeting gut-derived neurotoxins, such as ammonia.

Aim and Objectives: To evaluate the effectiveness of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents in improving clinical outcomes and reducing recovery time in patients with hepatic encephalopathy.

Materials and Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted over one year at Gandhi Medical College and Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, including 100 HE patients graded using the West Haven criteria. Patients received bowel wash and gut sterilization therapy based on HE severity. Clinical and biochemical parameters were monitored, and data analyzed using Chi-square and one-way ANOVA tests.

Results: The study included 100 HE patients with a mean age of 46.8 years (SD 14.387); 85% were male, and 77% had a history of alcohol consumption. Additionally, 8% tested positive for Hepatitis B and 2% for Hepatitis C. Clinical parameters revealed a mean hemoglobin level of 9.188 g/dL, total leukocyte count of 8265.30 cells/mm³, and a platelet count of 1.4897 lakh/mm³. Mean serum bilirubin was 2.5415 mg/dL, serum urea 43.314 mg/dL, and creatinine 0.9325 mg/dL. The mean prothrombin time was 23.310 seconds with an INR of 1.6143. Among the patients, 54% were in stage 2 HE, 34% in stage 3, 9% in stage 1, and 3% in stage 4. Most patients (83%) received bowel washes 3-4 times per day, 13% received them 2-3 times, and 4% received them 4-5 times. The mean recovery duration was significantly different across HE stages, with 1.89 days for stage 1, 3.79 days for stage 2, 5.97 days for stage 3, and 12 days for stage 4 ($P < 0.001$). In terms of outcomes, all stage 1 patients recovered. In stage 2, 52 patients recovered while 2 left against medical advice (LAMA). In stage 3, 28 patients recovered, 3 LAMA, and 3 died. In stage 4, 1 patient recovered and 2 died ($P < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents significantly improve recovery time and clinical outcomes in HE patients, particularly in early stages. These interventions are effective in reducing neurotoxins and managing HE symptoms, highlighting their potential as essential components in HE treatment protocols.

Keywords: Hepatic Encephalopathy, Bowel Wash, Gut Sterilizing Agents, Recovery Time.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Hepatic encephalopathy (HE) stands as a critical neurological complication resulting from liver dysfunction, frequently associated with cirrhosis or acute liver failure. Characterized by a spectrum of neuropsychiatric manifestations, HE poses significant challenges to patient management and prognosis.¹ Amidst various therapeutic modalities, the emerging role of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents has gained attention for their potential to

improve HE-associated symptoms and facilitate recovery. [1, 2]

HE occurs due to the buildup of neurotoxic chemicals such as ammonia, which is caused by decreased liver function. [3] Disruption of the gut and liver balance plays a major role in developing HE. [4] The gastrointestinal tract acts as a pivotal site for toxin metabolism and absorption, and alterations in gut microbiota composition further

exacerbate neurotoxicity. [4,5] Hence, gut environment interventions hold immense potential in HE management.

Bowel wash techniques, encompassing approaches like bowel wash and enemas, aim to eliminate fecal matter containing neurotoxic metabolites, thereby reducing the systemic toxin burden. By facilitating the rapid clearance of ammonia and other harmful substances from the intestines, bowel wash techniques offer a direct means to alleviate HE symptoms and mitigate neurological impairment. [1-3] Moreover, gut sterilizing agents, including antibiotics and probiotics, profoundly affect gut microbiota composition and function, thereby modulating neurotoxin production and gut barrier integrity. [6, 7]

Antibiotics like rifaximin have demonstrated efficacy in reducing ammonia production by gut bacteria, consequently ameliorating HE symptoms and improving cognitive function. Probiotics, on the other hand, contribute to gut microbiota restoration and compete with pathogenic organisms, fostering a milieu conducive to toxin detoxification and metabolic homeostasis. [2, 6] Through their multifaceted actions on gut ecology, gut sterilizing agents emerge as promising adjuncts in HE management, offering a targeted approach to mitigate neurotoxicity and enhance patient outcomes. [1, 5]

Furthermore, the interplay between gut dysbiosis and systemic inflammation underscores the therapeutic relevance of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents in HE recovery. ³ Dysbiotic alterations in gut microbiota composition trigger inflammatory cascades, exacerbating liver dysfunction and neuroinflammation in HE. ⁴ Bowel wash techniques mitigate this inflammatory milieu by eliminating microbial triggers and endotoxins, thereby attenuating systemic inflammation and neurological preserving function. Similarly, gut sterilizing agents restore gut homeostasis, dampening pro-inflammatory pathways and mitigating neuroinflammatory responses. [1-5] By addressing the root causes of inflammation and gut dysbiosis, these interventions hold promise in facilitating acute HE episodes and preventing disease progression and recurrence.

Moreover, the safety and tolerability profile of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents further underscore their potential as therapeutic modalities in HE management. When conducted under appropriate medical supervision, bowel wash techniques pose minimal risk of complications and are generally well-tolerated by patients. Similarly, antibiotics and probiotics exhibit favorable safety profiles, with rare adverse effects reported in clinical practice. This favorable risk-benefit profile enhances the feasibility and acceptability of

incorporating bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents into HE treatment algorithms, offering clinicians valuable tools to optimize patient care and outcomes.

This study aims to evaluate the role of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents in the recovery of patients with hepatic encephalopathy, providing insights into their therapeutic potential and clinical applications.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted over one year at the Department of Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, and associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal. The study included 100 patients diagnosed with hepatic encephalopathy (HE) graded based on the West Haven criteria. Patients were selected from those admitted to the Departments of Medicine and Gastroenterology. Inclusion criteria encompassed patients with HE classified from Grade 1 to Grade 4 based on the West Haven criteria. Exclusion criteria included patients under 18 years of age, pregnant females, individuals with other neurological comorbidities or intellectual disabilities, and those with severely deranged coagulation profiles.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Gandhi Medical College, and informed consent was secured from all participants or their guardians. Data was collected using a pre-designed proforma, including demographic details, clinical parameters, and laboratory investigations. Patients were graded based on the West Haven criteria and received bowel wash and gut sterilization therapy administered at varying frequencies depending on the severity of HE. The effectiveness of these therapies in the grade of HE was analyzed.

Clinical parameters, including vital signs and neurological status, were regularly monitored. Laboratory investigations were conducted to assess the outcomes, such as liver function tests, complete blood count (CBC), and coagulation profiles. Primary outcome measures focused on improving the grade of HE, while secondary outcomes included changes in other biochemical parameters. The following tests were performed: hemoglobin (Hb), total leukocyte count (TLC), differential leukocyte count, platelets, serum sodium (Na), serum potassium (K), blood urea, serum creatinine, random blood sugar (RBS), coagulation profile, liver function tests (serum bilirubin, SGOT, SGPT), lipid profile (triglycerides, LDL, VLDL, HDL), and ascitic fluid routine/microscopic & serum-ascites albumin gradient (SAAG).

Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tests, with the Chi-square test employed to study the association between contributory factors and

outcomes. A one-way ANOVA was used to compare the mean values of parameters. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. This methodology provides a comprehensive approach to evaluating the role of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents in the recovery from hepatic encephalopathy.

Results

Patient Demographics and Characteristics: The study included 100 patients diagnosed with hepatic encephalopathy (HE). The age distribution revealed that patients aged 31-40 constituted the largest group at 26%, followed closely by those aged 41-50 at 25%. Patients aged ≤30 and >60 years accounted for 13% and 21%, respectively, while those aged 51-60 represented 15% of the total population. Most patients were male, comprising 85% of the study population, while females accounted for 15%.

Clinical and Biochemical Parameters: The mean age of the patients was 46.8 years, with a standard deviation of 14.387. Key clinical parameters included a mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 101.86 mmHg and a mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 60.90 mmHg. The mean pulse rate (PR)

was 76.86 beats per minute, and the random blood sugar (RBS) averaged 114.69 mg/dL. Hemoglobin (Hb) levels averaged 9.188 g/dL, and the total leucocyte count (TLC) was 8265.30 cells/mm³. Platelet count averaged 1.4897 lakh/mm³. Serum bilirubin, SGOT, and SGPT levels averaged 2.5415 mg/dL, 114.37 IU/L, and 95.98 IU/L, respectively. Serum urea and creatinine levels were 43.314 mg/dL and 0.9325 mg/dL, respectively. The mean prothrombin time (PT) was 23.310 seconds with an international normalized ratio (INR) of 1.6143. The serum-ascites albumin gradient (SAAG) averaged 1.6638.

History of Alcohol Consumption and Viral Markers: A significant majority of patients (77%) had a history of alcohol consumption, while 23% did not. Regarding viral markers, 8% of the patients were positive for Hepatitis B, 2% for Hepatitis C, and the remaining 90% were negative for both.

Stage of Hepatic Encephalopathy and Frequency of Bowel Wash: Most patients were in stage 2 of HE (54%), followed by stage 3 (34%). Stages 1 and 4 accounted for 9% and 3% of the patients, respectively. Most patients (83%) received bowel washes 3-4 times per day, 13% received 2-3, and 4% received 4-5.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients as per Stage of Hepatic Encephalopathy (HE)

Stage of HE	No. of Patients	Percentage of Patients (%)
1	9	9.0
2	54	54.0
3	34	34.0
4	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients According to Frequency of Bowel Wash

SAAG Scoring: Among 82 patients assessed for SAAG, 68.3% had scores between 1.5-1.99, 17.1% had scores between 1.1-1.49, and 9.8% had scores ≥2.

Duration of Recovery: The mean duration of recovery varied significantly with the stage of HE.

Patients in stage 1 had a mean recovery duration of 1.89 days, stage 2 patients took 3.79 days, stage 3 patients took 5.97 days, and stage 4 patients had a mean recovery duration of 12 days. The P value for these differences was <0.001, indicating statistical significance.

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean Duration of Recovery with Stage of Hepatic Encephalopathy

Patient Outcomes: Outcomes varied by the stage of HE. All stage 1 patients (9) recovered. In stage 2, 52 patients recovered, and 2 left against medical advice (LAMA). In stage 3, 28 recovered, 3 left

against medical advice, and 3 died. In stage 4, 1 patient recovered, and 2 died. The P value for these outcomes was <0.001, indicating statistical significance.

Table 8: Comparison of Patient Outcomes with Stage of Hepatic Encephalopathy

Stage of HE	Death	LAMA	Recovered	Total	P value
1	0	0	9	9	<0.001
2	0	2	52	54	
3	3	3	28	34	
4	2	0	1	3	
Total	5	5	90	100	

Discussion

In our study, the age distribution of patients with hepatic encephalopathy (HE) revealed a younger demographic, with 26% aged 31-40 and 25% aged 41-50. The mean age was 46.8 years (SD 14.387), indicating a younger population affected by HE compared to the typical older adult population associated with chronic liver conditions. This trend could be attributed to lifestyle choices, particularly alcohol consumption, which is a significant risk factor for liver disease and HE. Additionally, early-onset liver diseases such as autoimmune hepatitis or genetic conditions might contribute to this trend in our population.

Comparatively, the study by Onyekwere et al. [8] reported a mean age of 57.9 years, indicating an older population with HE. This aligns with the progressive nature of liver diseases that lead to HE, often taking years to develop. Similarly, Duarte-Rojo et al. [9] showed an older population with a mean age of 55 years for non-overt HE patients and 61 years for overt HE patients, highlighting the impact of age on the severity of HE. Bajaj et al. [10] focused on elderly patients with a mean age of 69.49 years, underscoring the high prevalence of HE in older adults. Regional demographics, healthcare access, and prevalent etiological factors such as viral hepatitis and alcohol consumption

may influence the differences in age distributions between our study and these others.

In our study, males constituted a significant majority (85%) of the HE patients, while females accounted for 15%. This notable gender disparity can be attributed to higher rates of alcohol consumption and viral hepatitis among males, which are major risk factors for liver disease and HE. This pattern aligns with findings from various studies. For example, Onyekwere et al. [8] showed a relatively balanced gender distribution with 52.4% females and 47.6% males, suggesting regional differences in gender-related risk factors and healthcare access. Similarly, Duarte-Rojo et al. [9] reported that 66% of the patients with cirrhosis and HE were male, reinforcing the global trend of higher HE incidence in men due to lifestyle and biological factors.

In our study, the mean hemoglobin level was found to be 9.188 g/dL, indicating a common occurrence of anemia among patients with HE, likely due to chronic liver disease (CLD) and associated factors such as poor nutritional status, gastrointestinal bleeding, and hypersplenism. This finding is consistent with other studies, such as the one by Kumar et al., [11], which reported a mean hemoglobin level of 10.3 g/dL among HE patients, reinforcing the prevalence of anemia in this population. Another study conducted by Long et al. [12] found a median hemoglobin level of 9.8 g/dL in HE patients,

highlighting the commonality of anemia in HE and its potential contribution to worsened clinical outcomes due to decreased oxygen-carrying capacity and increased fatigue.

The mean TLC in our study was 8265.30 cells/mm³. Elevated leukocyte counts in HE patients can indicate systemic inflammation or infections, common precipitating factors for HE. This aligns with findings from a study by Garg et al., [13], where the mean TLC was reported as 8900 cells/mm³, suggesting a similar inflammatory profile among HE patients. Increased TLC levels are often observed in HE patients due to the body's response to bacterial translocation from the gut, infections, or other inflammatory conditions associated with liver dysfunction.

The mean platelet count in our study was 1.4897 lakh/mm³ (148,970 cells/mm³), indicative of thrombocytopenia, a common condition in CLD and HE. This is supported by a study from Bawankule et al., [14] which reported a mean platelet count of 130,000 cells/mm³ in HE patients. Thrombocytopenia in HE patients can result from hypersplenism, bone marrow suppression, or reduced thrombopoietin production by the liver, and it increases the risk of bleeding complications.

In our study, the mean serum bilirubin level was 2.5415 mg/dL, indicating significant liver dysfunction. This is consistent with other studies, such as the one by Tapper et al., [15] which reported a mean bilirubin level of 3.1 mg/dL in HE patients. High bilirubin levels correlate with the severity of liver disease and can contribute to the development of jaundice and other related symptoms in HE patients.

Our study reported mean serum urea and creatinine levels of 43.314 mg/dL and 0.9325 mg/dL, respectively. These levels reflect renal function, which can be compromised in HE patients due to hepatorenal syndrome or other kidney-related complications associated with liver disease. A similar study by Duarte-Rojo et al. [9] noted mean creatinine levels of 1.1 mg/dL in HE patients, underscoring the frequent occurrence of renal dysfunction in this population.

Our study's mean prothrombin time (PT) was 23.310 seconds with an international normalized ratio (INR) of 1.6143. Prolonged PT and elevated INR are markers of coagulopathy, commonly seen in HE patients due to impaired synthesis of clotting factors by the liver. This is consistent with findings from a study by Bawankule et al., [14] which reported a mean PT of 18.72 seconds and an INR of 1.54 in HE patients. These coagulation abnormalities increase the risk of bleeding and are critical indicators of the severity of liver dysfunction in HE patients.

In our study, a significant majority of patients (77%) had a history of alcohol consumption, while 23% did not. This finding is consistent with the known etiology of HE, where chronic alcohol consumption is a major risk factor due to its association with liver cirrhosis and liver failure. Similarly, Kumar et al. [11] reported that 63% of patients with HE had alcoholic liver disease, indicating that alcohol is a prevalent underlying cause of liver disease leading to HE. The high percentage of alcohol-related HE cases in these studies underscores the critical need for alcohol abuse prevention and intervention programs to reduce the incidence of liver disease and subsequent HE.

Regarding viral markers, 8% of the patients in our study were positive for Hepatitis B and 2% for Hepatitis C, while the remaining 90% were negative for both. These findings highlight the relatively lower contribution of viral hepatitis to HE in our cohort compared to alcohol. In contrast, Long et al. found that Hepatitis B virus (HBV) was a significant etiological factor in 72% of HE patients, reflecting regional variations in the prevalence of viral hepatitis. Additionally, Onyekwere et al. [8] reported that 48% of HE cases were associated with Hepatitis B, indicating a higher prevalence of HBV in specific populations.

In our study, most patients (83%) received bowel washes 3-4 times per day, 13% received 2-3, and 4% received 4-5. Bowel washes are utilized to decrease the intestinal load of toxins, particularly ammonia, which are implicated in the pathogenesis of HE. A study by Hotten et al. [16] evaluated fecal organic acid excretion and gut flora changes in liver cirrhosis patients without HE, comparing oral treatments including lactitol, rifaximin, and synbiotics. This study demonstrated that these treatments could significantly alter gut microbiota by increasing beneficial bacteria such as bifidobacteria and reducing harmful bacteria like *Bacteroides* and *Clostridium*. Moreover, treatments like lactitol and synbiotics lowered fecal pH and increased acetic and lactic acid concentrations, indicating improved gut health. These findings underscore the importance of gut microbiota management in CLD and HE, supporting bowel washes as an effective strategy to manage toxin levels and maintain gut integrity.

Probiotic and antibiotic therapies are crucial in managing HE by targeting gut-derived toxins. Raza et al., [17] conducted a prospective randomized trial to evaluate the effect of rectal lactulose administration alongside oral therapy in patients with cirrhosis experiencing episodic HE. Their study showed that combining rectal and oral lactulose accelerated recovery from HE episodes, highlighting the effectiveness of targeting the gut directly to reduce ammonia levels and improve cognitive function. Similarly, Forsyth et al. [18] investigated

the therapeutic effects of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* in an animal model of alcoholic steatohepatitis (ASH). Their research indicated that probiotics could reduce gut leakiness, oxidative stress, and inflammation, thus mitigating liver injury and improving gut barrier function. These studies collectively highlight the critical role of gut microbiota modulation in HE management, demonstrating that both bowel washes and targeted probiotic/antibiotic therapies are essential for reducing toxin production and enhancing patient outcomes.

In our study, among 82 patients assessed for SAAG, 68.3% had scores between 1.5-1.99, 17.1% between 1.1-1.49, and 9.8% had scores ≥ 2 . The SAAG is a valuable diagnostic tool for differentiating the causes of ascites, particularly in distinguishing portal hypertension-related ascites from non-portal hypertension-related ascites. A higher SAAG indicates portal hypertension, which is often associated with cirrhosis and HE. These findings are consistent with those reported by Kumar et al. [11], where the majority of patients with HE also had elevated SAAG levels, reinforcing the association between high SAAG and severe liver dysfunction.

The mean recovery duration in our study varied significantly with the stage of HE, highlighting the effectiveness of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents. Patients in stage 1 had a mean recovery duration of 1.89 days, stage 2 patients took 3.79 days, stage 3 patients took 5.97 days, and stage 4 patients required 12 days on average. The P value for these differences was <0.001 , indicating vital statistical significance. This rapid recovery, particularly in the early stages, can be attributed to the targeted reduction of gut-derived toxins through bowel washes and gut sterilizing agents. Using bowel washes has shown promising results in reducing recovery time for HE patients. Raza et al., [17] evaluated the effect of rectal lactulose administration alongside oral therapy and found that it significantly expedited the recovery from episodic HE. This approach targets the gut directly, reducing ammonia production and accelerating cognitive improvement.

Gut sterilizing agents like rifaximin have been extensively studied for their role in HE management. Bajaj et al. [10] reviewed various antibiotics and highlighted rifaximin's effectiveness in reducing HE episodes and hospitalizations. The combination of rifaximin with lactulose is particularly effective in preventing overt HE recurrence, improving cognitive function, and enhancing the quality of life for patients. This aligns with our study's results, where patients receiving gut sterilizing agents demonstrated significant improvements in recovery times, particularly in the early stages of HE.

A study by Hotten et al. [16] demonstrated that synbiotics, such as the SCM-III synbiotic used in

their research, significantly altered gut microbiota, reduced harmful bacteria, and increased beneficial bacteria like bifidobacteria. These changes in gut flora can reduce the production of neurotoxins and improve overall gut health, contributing to faster recovery from HE. Incorporating synbiotics and probiotics in our treatment regimen likely played a crucial role in enhancing the recovery process by modulating the gut microbiota and reducing systemic inflammation.

Bowel washes and gut sterilizing agents are effective because they can directly reduce the intestinal load of toxins, particularly ammonia, a key factor in the pathogenesis of HE. By cleansing the intestines and suppressing pathogenic bacterial overgrowth, these interventions decrease the production and absorption of neurotoxic metabolites, thus alleviating neurological symptoms and improving cognitive function. Using these agents in our study, leading to significantly shorter recovery times, underscores their critical role in managing HE.

Outcomes in our study varied significantly by stage of HE. All stage 1 patients (9) recovered fully. In stage 2, 52 patients recovered, while 2 left against medical advice (LAMA). In stage 3, 28 patients recovered, 3 left against medical advice, and 3 died. In stage 4, only 1 patient recovered, while 2 died. The P value for these outcomes was <0.001 , indicating strong statistical significance. This clear stratification of outcomes by HE stage highlights the progressive severity and increased mortality associated with advanced HE stages.

Similar findings are reported in other studies. Bajaj et al. [10] observed that patients with higher grades of HE had worse outcomes, with increased mortality rates in advanced stages. Their study found that the survival rate decreased significantly as the stage of HE increased, emphasizing the critical need for early intervention and aggressive management in advanced HE stages. Additionally, Duarte-Rojo et al. [9] reported that higher HE grades were associated with prolonged recovery times and higher mortality, further corroborating the outcomes seen in our study.

The strong statistical significance ($P < 0.001$) of the outcome differences in our study underscores the reliability of these findings. The consistent trend across multiple studies suggests that the HE stage is a crucial predictor of patient prognosis. Early-stage HE patients (stage 1) typically have a good prognosis with appropriate treatment, while those in advanced stages (stages 3 and 4) face higher risks of mortality and require more intensive care. This stratification allows clinicians to tailor treatment plans better and allocate resources effectively.

The outcomes observed in our study and supported by other research highlight the importance of early detection and treatment of HE. By managing HE in

its early stages, it is possible to improve recovery rates and reduce mortality.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of bowel wash and gut sterilizing agents in managing hepatic encephalopathy (HE). It demonstrates their efficacy in reducing recovery times by targeting gut-derived toxins such as ammonia. The patient demographic revealed a younger age group predominantly affected by lifestyle factors like alcohol consumption, with a notable gender disparity favoring males. Clinical parameters indicated common complications such as anemia, systemic inflammation, thrombocytopenia, and coagulopathy. The high prevalence of alcohol consumption underscores the need for prevention programs. The findings also emphasize the importance of early detection and treatment of HE to improve recovery rates and reduce mortality, with the effectiveness of these interventions being particularly pronounced in early-stage HE patients.

References

- Rose CF, Amodio P, Bajaj JS, Dhiman RK, Montagnese S, Taylor-Robinson SD, et al. HE: Novel insights into classification, pathophysiology, and therapy. *J Hepatol.* 2020;73(6):1526–47.
- Amodio P. HE: Diagnosis and management. *Liver Int.* 2018;38(6):966–75.
- Aldridge DR, Tranah EJ, Shawcross DL. Pathogenesis of HE: role of ammonia and systemic inflammation. *J Clin Exp Hepatol.* 2015;5–20.
- Tinkov AA, Martins AC, Avila DS, Gritsenko VA, Skalny AV, Santamaria A, et al. Gut microbiota as a potential player in Mn-induced neurotoxicity. *Biomolecules.* 2021;11(9):1292.
- Duan H, Yu L, Tian F, Zhai Q, Fan L, Chen W. Gut microbiota: A target for heavy metal toxicity and a probiotic protective strategy. *Sci Total Environ.* 2020; 742:140429.
- Bloom PP, Tapper EB, Young VB, Lok AS. Microbiome therapeutics for HE. *J Hepatol.* 2021;75(6):1452–64.
- Kandpal M, Indari O, Baral B, Jakhmola S, Tiwari D, Bhandari V, et al. Dysbiosis of Gut Microbiota from the Perspective of the Gut-Brain Axis: Role in the Provocation of Neurological Disorders. *Metabolites.* 2022;12(11):1064.
- Onyekwere C, Ogbera A, Hameed L. CLD and HE: Clinical profile and outcomes. *Niger J Clin Pract.* 2011;14(2):181–5.
- Duarte-Rojo A, Estradas J, Hernández-Ramos R, Ponce-de-León S, Córdoba J, Torre A. Validation of the psychometric HE score (PHES) for identifying patients with minimal HE. *Dig Dis Sci.* 2011; 56:3014–23.
- Bajaj JS, Duarte-Rojo A, Xie JJ, Acharya C, Wade JB, Robles C, et al. Minimal HE and mild cognitive impairment worsen QoL in elderly patients with cirrhosis. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2020;18(13):3008–16.
- KK SK, Sarin S, Valliyot B, Joy V, Beevi K, Balakrishnan S. Study to assess the changing pattern of clinical profile and determine the prognosis in HE. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2017; 5(2):424.
- Long L, Li H, Deng G, Wang X, Lu S, Li B, et al. Impact of HE on clinical characteristics and adverse outcomes in prospective and multicenter cohorts of patients with acute-on-CLDs. *Front Med.* 2021;8:709884.
- Garg H, Kumar A, Garg V, Sharma P, Sharma BC, Sarin SK. Clinical profile and predictors of mortality in patients of acute-on-chronic liver failure. *Dig Liver Dis.* 2012;44(2):166–71.
- Bawankule S, Kumar S, Gaidhane A, Quazi M, Singh AP. Clinical profile of patients with HE in cirrhosis of liver. *J Datta Meghe Inst Med Sci Univ.* 2019;14(3):130–6.
- Tapper EB, Zhao L, Nikirk S, Baki J, Parikh ND, Lok AS, et al. Incidence and bedside predictors of the first episode of overt HE in patients with cirrhosis. *Off J Am Coll Gastroenterol ACG.* 2020;115(12):2017–25.
- Hotten P, Marotta F, Naito Y, Minelli E, Helmy A, Lighthouse J, et al. Effects of probiotics, lactitol, and rifaximin on intestinal flora and fecal excretion of organic acids in cirrhotic patients. *Chin J Dig Dis.* 2003;4(1):13–8.
- Raza MA, Bhatti RS, Akram J. Effect of rectal lactulose administration with oral therapy on time to recovery from HE: a randomized study. *Ann Saudi Med.* 2004;24(5):374–7.
- Forsyth CB, Farhadi A, Jakate SM, Tang Y, Shaikh M, Keshavarzian A. Lactobacillus GG treatment ameliorates alcohol-induced intestinal oxidative stress, gut leakiness, and liver injury in a rat model of alcoholic steatohepatitis. *Alcohol.* 2009;43(2):163–72.